

Research of static and dynamic characteristics of a process system ‘electric drive-fluid-handling machine-pipeline’

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ABSTRACT

The paper offers the obtained quantitative assessment of the performance and energy parameters of a process system composed of an asynchronous motor, a fluid-handling machine and a pipeline when using two methods of performance control, in particular, throttling and speed control methods. Taking into account nonlinearity of mathematical representation of fluid-handling machines and asynchronous drive motors, the starting conditions were analysed using nonlinear differential calculus. The calculations for the models were performed using the MATLAB software package. Transient profiles of flow and head, stator current, angular frequency and torque of an asynchronous motor were obtained at pump startup and control of pump capacity. It has been found that the developed mathematical model of a process system composed of an asynchronous motor, a fluid-handling machine and a pipeline allows obtaining quantitative estimation of the performance and energy parameters of the unit when using two methods of the pump capacity control. The use of frequency method allows to decrease the pump rotation speed and significantly reduce the power consumed by the unit and provide energy-saving mode of operation, the economic efficiency of which depends on the range of feed control.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The regulation of liquid and gas flows conveyed by pipelines is highly significant. During the term of applications, the fluids being transported are contained within tanks, equipment, and pipelines. Simultaneously, it is acknowledged that pipelines, valves, and other apparatuses generate resistance to the movement of fluids. The presence of mass in flowing liquids or gasses results in the resistance of friction and inertia against the forces driving the motion. The dynamic mathematical models of fluid flows in pipelines should consider the inertial properties of the fluid.

The transient performances, in terms of duration, processing accuracy of control actions, overregulation, and other factors, should satisfy certain requirements while considering two different pumping capacity values. Preventing water hammer and vibrations is a crucial concern in liquid flows. Hence, a dynamic mathematical portrayal of fluids is essential for the advancement of effective flow control systems for pipelines. These models should accurately represent the correlation between external pressure, characteristics of the transported fluid, pipeline and control equipment parameters, and the flow rate.

Fluid-handling machines, also known as turbo-mechanisms, are responsible for efficiently moving enormous quantities of liquid and gas via pipelines. This equipment includes pumps, fans, pressure blowers, and compressors. Researchers are now studying issues connected to the transportation of material media through pipelines. This is important since choosing the right capacity control strategy for these systems can lead to significant energy savings. The mechanical energy exerted on a fluid-handling machine during its operation is transformed into both potential and kinetic energy of the transported material. Energy losses are present in every component of the drive-fluid-handling machine-pipeline process chain.

Various calculations suggest that the electric drives used in fluid-handling devices account for around 25% to 30% of the total global electricity generation [1], [2]. Hence, it is economically justifiable to develop a dependable and sufficient mathematical model for the processes taking place in electric drives of fluid-handling equipment. The authors in [3]–[9] discuss the problems associated with energy efficient capacity control of fluid-handling equipment. Implementation details of a special nature are also taken into account in the range of references [10]–[17]. We will employ the methodologies described in [18] to construct mathematical models of the components involved in the electric drive - fluid-handling equipment pipeline process flow.

2. METHOD AND MODEL OF A PROCESS SYSTEM ‘ASYNCHRONOUS MOTOR-FLUID-HANDLING MACHINE-PIPELINE’

The main process parameters of fluid-handling machine are flow and head. These parameters depend on the rotation speed of the machine and the resistance of the pipeline through which the liquid or gas flows. In steady-state mode, the operating point of a pump or fan is defined as the point of intersection of the Q-H characteristic of the machine and the characteristic of the pipeline. When regulating the performance of the fluid-handling machine by throttling method, the position of the pipeline characteristic changes, and when controlling the speed of the drive motor, the Q-H characteristic of the machine changes its position. When the speed is reduced, the Q-H characteristic of the machine moves downwards, while the flow and head values at the operating point decrease. The useful power consumed by the fluid-handling machine is proportional to the product of flow and head. Therefore, when the rotation speed is reduced, the power consumed from the mains decreases, and when using the throttling method, this power increases in proportion to the increase in head. To quantify these methods of pump capacity control, mathematical models have been developed, which take into account the dynamic characteristics of the elements of the process system. Equation of liquid or gas flow in a pipeline [19]–[21]:

$$H - H_{Mag} = \frac{1}{H_1} \frac{dQ}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where H is the head (pressure) at the inlet of the machine, Pa; H_{Mag} is the characteristic of the pipeline, Pa; $\frac{1}{A_1} \frac{dQ}{dt}$ is the dynamic head in the pipeline.

Characteristic of the pipeline taking into account the static head is as (2):

$$H_{Mag} = (H_c + \frac{A_2}{A_1}) Q^2 \quad (2)$$

where H_c is the static head in the pipeline. Design and process parameter A_1 is determined from (3):

$$A_1 = \frac{S}{L\gamma} \quad (3)$$

where $S = \pi d^2/4$ is the equivalent cross-sectional area of the pipeline, m^2 ; d is the equivalent diameter of the pipeline, m; L is the equivalent length of the pipeline, m; γ is the density of the pumped liquid or gas, kg/m^3 .

The resistance factor of the pipeline A_2 may be calculated from the datasheet specifications of the fluid-handling machine for the operating point $H=H_H$ and $Q=Q_H$.

$$A_2 = \frac{A_1(H_H - H_c)}{Q_H^2} \quad (4)$$

Laplace transformation of (1) followed by the use of (1) to (4) allow to obtain the fluid-handling machine model shown in Figure 1. Let us use parameter values of the existing pump and pipeline. Technical

and design data of the pump and pipeline: pump type SA075T; $Q_H=4,680 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $H_H=9.8 \text{ m}$, $H_c=0 \text{ m}$, $\omega_H=293 \text{ 1/s}$, $d=50 \text{ mm}=0.05 \text{ m}$, $L=10 \text{ m}$, $S=0.0019625 \text{ m}^2$, $K=177.5147 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}/\text{m}^6$, $K_1=1.4543 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}^2$, $A_1=19.625 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$, $A_2=11522.574 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}^2/\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^3$. The block model of the regulated electric drive of the pump unit, containing frequency converter (FC), pump and drive motor (asynchronous motor) is shown in Figure 2. The flow diagram contains flow setting device SQ, FC PH, asynchronous motor ad, pump, and measuring unit B.

Figure 1. Model of the fluid-handling machine and pipeline

Figure 2. Block model of the process system and FC

Modern FCs are produced using microprocessor-based control system and contain transistorized power part. Such converter as a link of the control system can be represented by instantaneous element with two control channels: voltage and frequency [22]–[25]. At scalar control of such converter for the fan type loads, a nonlinear control law between voltage and frequency is chosen. Such law is chosen in the FC model shown in Figure 3.

The FC model consists of a voltage setting device, which includes two blocks of factors $K_d=0.6$ and $K_q=0.8$ determining the amplitude and initial phase of the voltage; a frequency setting device, which includes a time block and a block for setting the angular frequency of the stator field $\omega_1=2\pi f_1$; coordinate converter unit (PK) for converting rotating coordinates x and y into stationary coordinates α and β ; phase converter unit (PF) for converting two-phase coordinate system α, β into three-phase A, B, C. The reference signal from the flow valve is fed to the input of the frequency setting device. Therefore, the current frequency at the PF output will be proportional to the reference signal. A multiplier unit is installed at the input of the voltage setting device, so the torque developed by the motor will correspond to the fan load. The model of process

system with FC for pump SA075T is shown in Figure 4. The model contains an asynchronous motor (type 4A63B293) with the following nominal data: $P_H=0.55$ kW; $U_H=230/400$ V; $I_H=3/1.5$ A; $n_H=2850$ rev/min; $\eta_H=0.73\%$; $\cos\phi_H=0.98$; $R_S=19.066$ Ohm; $R_R=14.079$ Ohm.

Figure 3. FC model

Figure 4. Model of a process system and FC

The model is build according to the block structure shown in Figure 2. The pump model is built using multiplier unit, multiplier-division blocks, adder units, transfer factor units K1...K5, constant value units A1, A2 and C, units of measuring instruments. The pump model takes into account the change in the efficiency of the mechanism during flow control. For this purpose, the factors K2 and K3 are used. The pump model at capacity control by throttling method contained an adjustable factor A2, and at frequency control this factor remains unchanged: $A2=11152.574=const.$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transients (oscillograms) for various parameters of the electric drive and pump when controlling the pump capacity by throttling method and by frequency speed control method were compared. Figure 5 shows the transients of pump head and flow rate at start-up and pump capacity control as shown in Figure 5(a) by throttling method and Figure 5(b) by frequency control. Obtained oscillograms shows that at control of the pump capacity by both methods the flow rate in a steady-state mode is identical and varies within the limits from nominal value of 4.7 m³/h to minimum value of 2.17 m³/h. when using throttling method for control, the pump head increases 1.26 times and when using frequency control method, the pump head decreases 4.6 time.

Analysis of the received oscillograms allows to determine that at control of the pump capacity by both methods the flow rate in a steady-state mode is identical and varies within the limits from nominal value of 4.7 m³/h to minimum value of 2.17 m³/h; however, the head varies in a different way:

- When using throttling method for control, the pump head increases 1.26 times from 9.73 m to 12.23 m;

- When using frequency control method for control, the pump head decreases 4.6 time from 9.73 m to 2.11 m.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Pump head and flow transient at start-up and capacity control (a) by throttling method and (b) by frequency control methods

Figure 6 shows transients on stator current, angular rotation speed and motor torques at start-up and control of the pump capacity as shown in Figure 6(a) by throttling and Figure 6(b) frequency control methods. Obtained oscillograms shows that at control of the pump capacity within the limits from nominal value of 4.7 m³/h to minimum value of 2.17 m³/h, the stator current and motor torque are decreased but the speed of the motor remains constant by using throttling method of control, whereas by using the frequency control method the torque and current are more decreased than by using throttling method.

Analysis of the received oscillograms allows to determine that at control of the pump capacity within the limits from nominal value of 4.7 m³/h to minimum value of 2.17 m³/h:

- By throttling method, the stator current of asynchronous motor decreases from 0.755 A to 0.734 A; pump speed almost does not change; asynchronous motor torque decreases from 0.732 and to 0.646 Nm;
- By frequency control method, the stator current of asynchronous motor decreases from 0.755 A to 0.43 A; asynchronous motor torque decreases 0.732 to 0.25 Nm.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Transients on starter current, angular rotation frequency ω and torque of asynchronous motor M at start-up and control of the pump capacity (a) by throttling and (b) frequency control methods

Figure 7 shows the time variation of torque and power of resistance forces on the shaft of asynchronous motor start-up and pump capacity control as shown in Figure 7(a) by throttling and Figure 7(b)

frequency control methods. Obtained oscillograms shows that at control of the pump capacity within the limits from nominal value of 4.7 m³/h to minimum value of 2.17 m³/h, the torque of resistance on the shaft of the asynchronous motor reduces, and power of resistance forces also reduces, but by using the frequency control method the torque of resistance on the shaft of the asynchronous motor reduces, and power of resistance forces are more decreased than by the using throttling method. Analysis of the received oscillograms allows to determine that at control of the pump capacity within the limits from nominal value of 4.7 m³/h to minimum value of 2.7 m³/h:

- By throttling method, the torque of resistance on the shaft of asynchronous motor reduces from 0.579 to 0.4925 Nm; power of resistance forces reduces from 176.7 to 150.8 J;
- By frequency control method, the torque of resistance on the shaft of asynchronous motor reduces from 0.579 to 0.1834 Nm; power of resistance forces reduces from 176.7 to 26 J.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Oscillograms of the torque and power of resistance forces on the shaft of asynchronous motor at start-up and control of the pump capacity (a) by throttling and (b) frequency control methods

4. CONCLUSION

Two methods for control of the performance of the process system composed of an electric drive, a pump and a pipeline were compared. The research has shown that when the pump flow rate decreases by 2.17 times: i) head increases 1.26 times when controlling by the throttling method, and 4.6 times when controlling by frequency method; ii) stator current, torque and speed of asynchronous motor at throttling almost do not change, and at frequency method they decrease: current –1.77 times, torque –2.93 times, speed –2.15 times; iii) torque and power of resistance forces on the shaft of the asynchronous motor at throttling decreases 1.17 times, and at frequency method the moment of resistance forces decreases 3.15 times, and power 6.79 times. Thus, the developed mathematical model of the process system composed of an asynchronous motor, a fluid-handling machine and pipeline allows to obtain quantitative assessment of the performance and energy parameters of the unit using two methods of pump capacity control. Deployment of the frequency method allows to reduce the pump rotation speed, and significantly decrease the power consumed by the unit and provide for energy-saving mode of operation, the economic efficiency of which depends on the range of feed control.

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